

Malleable I/O Applications Modeling with ElastiSim

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Abstract— Parallel applications process large amounts of data leading to intensive parallel Input-Output (I/O) operations. These operations can exhibit different levels of complexity, including data access patterns, data consistency, I/O scalability, and others. Therefore, to use High-performance computing (HPC) systems efficiently and optimize the I/O performance, it is crucial to characterize the I/O behavior of the HPC applications. In this work, we have developed algorithms that can reproduce real applications through the ElastiSim simulator, putting the focus on their I/O behavior. ElastiSim is a batch-system simulator for malleable and evolving workloads. These simulated applications are generated based on I/O traces captured from real applications provided by the HPCIO database. We present a methodology that models applications and reproduces the original HPCIO traces. In addition, a malleable performance model for computation and I/O is presented. This model reflects the simulated application performance when the number of processes changes. We have conducted detailed case studies of real-world applications found in HPCIO to demonstrate how the modeling framework can provide insights into the performance characteristics of I/O applications. The results of the tests show the feasibility and the accuracy of the provided solution. As a practical application of the simulation framework, this work examines how interference between applications can decrease I/O performance and cause congestion over system resources.

Keywords— HPC I/O, application modeling, I/O characterization, malleability, performance model.

I. INTRODUCTION

Supercomputers are advancing computing power. As listed in Top500 [1], the top-ranked supercomputer has reached exascale peak performance. This recent surge in growth poses multiple challenges for developers of parallel applications. It is crucial to design programs that leverage such high performance. The HPC systems are designed to cater to the needs of applications that either require intensive processing or storage of large amounts of data. On the other hand, parallel applications often underperform on modern supercomputers due to several issues, such as load imbalance, resource contention, inefficient memory access, and network congestion. Also, applications are often limited in scalability by their parallel I/O performance. Therefore, it is essential to characterize I/O behavior in HPC applications to identify such performance bottlenecks [2], [3], [4].

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Modeling I/O workloads is necessary for evaluating storage architecture and I/O software stack (burst buffer configurations, I/O scheduling algorithms, etc.) through simulations. This helps to analyze the impact of specific workloads on particular storage system implementations. From the scheduling and task management side, the modeling of parallel applications benefits better scheduling decisions by helping the scheduler map the most proper nodes to a task. However, The design of hardware and input parameters are among the factors that can affect the performance of parallel applications, making it a challenge to create an accurate performance model [3], [5].

The performance analysis of parallel applications can follow the approach of profiling and summarizing the statistical data about the application execution. Such an approach provides a coarse-grained view of the application. In contrast, the tracing-based analysis captures performance data as a time series with fine-grained information. This methodology facilitates the identification of the real causes of performance decline. This makes trace analysis tools essential in identifying the underlying causes of I/O issues. Furthermore, analyzing the scalability of parallel programs becomes increasingly important as the number of cores in processors continues to rise. One approach to identifying scalability limitations is through simulation, which can be done with minimal impact on runtime [2].

In this work, we present a complete methodology for modeling I/O applications considering a changing number of processes (both static and malleable). We provide detailed case studies of real applications, and we demonstrate how the presented modeling framework is able to obtain insights of the platform I/O performance.

The major contributions of our work are:

- A technique for reproducing I/O traces from the HPCIO portal through a novel methodology that auto-calibrates applications in ElastiSim.
- A malleable performance model, for both CPU and IO, permits extending the original I/O traces to any number of processes considering malleable and non-malleable executions.
- An evaluation of real use case applications considering an I/O congestion scenario.

The article reminder is organized as follows: Section II provides an overview of the most relevant state of the art. Section III presents the proposed framework, including a description of the algorithms used

for the modeling. Section IV explains the application use cases, the system platform used, and the performance metrics employed in the evaluation. Finally, Section V summarizes the work and discusses future directions.

II. STATE OF THE ART

Several techniques exist for modeling and predicting I/O application performance in HPC systems. These techniques could follow the approach of statistics and analysis, predictive analytics, the replay-based approach, or workload generation tools [5]. Statistics and analysis techniques help to extract meaningful patterns from numerical data by collecting, classifying, and representing it. The collected data can include I/O traces, I/O characterization profiles, scheduler logs, server-side statistics, and other logs. Many studies use this approach. For example, Patel et al. in [6] performed a correlative analysis of the system to identify subtle relationships between different I/O activities and system components over time. MPItrace presented in [7] is a tracing tool that captures performance data of parallel applications. It provides more data by gathering information from uninstrumented regions of code. In [8], Statistics about the Lustre file system are collected on compute nodes, metadata, and object storage file system servers. These statistics are analyzed to understand HPC application I/O behavior. They aimed to determine typical I/O characteristics of I/O-heavy jobs and investigate if I/O contention affects system performance.

Other techniques for modeling I/O applications follow the predictive and analytics approaches. Such approaches aim to identify performance issues in advance by analyzing historical data. It employs statistical techniques such as data mining, predictive modeling, and machine learning. For example, the research presented in [9] is motivated by the observation that most high-performance computing (HPC) applications follow a pattern of initialization, repetitive processing, and termination phases. To predict the performance of these applications, the researchers rely heavily on the data defined during the initialization phase. This approach is specifically designed to model the execution time of parallel programs using random forest machine learning. Their evaluation experiments include three parallel applications Graph500, GalaxSee and SMG2000. Another work presented in [4] introduces an autotuning system designed mainly to hide the complexity of the I/O stack from the scientific application without compromising performance. Their system uses a sequential framework that first checks the I/O trace for a pattern match. If no match is found, the autotuning is used to initiate the modeling process.

Besides statistical and predictive analytics, other studies utilize the replay-based approach. This involves analyzing the historical application traces to generate a copy of the workload, which can replay the I/O behavior of the original application. The

authors of [10] proposed a mathematical model and a replay engine for analyzing and extrapolating trace data and verifying the accuracy of the extrapolated trace file. The workload generation is crucial for simulating storage systems, evaluating new research, and examining workload impact on specific system implementation. Snyder et al. in [3] proposed a technique to abstract HPC I/O workload from different sources (e.g., Darshan, Recorder, and CODES) to support I/O evaluation and analysis tools. Their approach aimed to help researchers identify the sources of workload by discussing various methods of workload generation based on the type of evaluation required. Their experiments showed that each method of workload generation has its advantages and disadvantages in terms of flexibility, accuracy, and ease of use.

This article explains the algorithms used in the *ElastiSim* simulator to replicate real applications, focusing on their I/O behavior. The simulated applications are created based on I/O traces collected from real applications, which are available in the HP-CIO database. The goal of application modeling is to analyze the malleability of the I/O application, which sets it apart from previous studies. A malleability performance model for computation and I/O is presented to achieve this, reflecting how the application behaves when the number of processes are adjusted. Furthermore, we studied and analyzed the I/O performance with interference between the parallel applications.

A. *Elastisim*

Experiments on real systems are expensive and time-consuming, so we used *ElastiSim* to evaluate our proposed scheduling algorithm. *ElastiSim* is a batch-system simulator for malleable workloads simulating jobs, applications, the scheduling algorithm, and the platform. It is a discrete-event simulator written in C++, based on the simulation framework *SimGrid* [11]. In contrast to other general-purpose simulators known in the literature, such as *Batsim* [12], *AccaSim* [13], or *Alea* [14], *ElastiSim* has built-in support for malleable jobs augmented with performance models, which we exploit to describe malleability in simulated applications. As *ElastiSim* also provides a Python interface to integrate custom scheduling algorithms, the simulation of scheduling scenarios introduces less overhead compared to simulators based on actual batch systems [15], [16].

To evaluate scheduling algorithms for large-scale distributed systems, *ElastiSim* introduces system actors and separates the concerns of platform simulations, user interaction (i.e., job submission), and the batch system—including the scheduling algorithm. As illustrated in Figure 1, *ElastiSim* provides interfaces to define the workload and the platform that executes it. To define the scheduling logic, users integrate their scheduling policies using the provided scheduling interface that runs in a separate process and constantly communicates with the simulation

Fig. 1: The architecture of ElastiSim. The scheduling algorithm runs as an external process and is in constant communication with the simulation process.

process to forward scheduling decisions. We used the Python interface of ElastiSim to develop the algorithms proposed in this work.

ElastiSim’s workload model comprises jobs and their corresponding application model. While jobs define high-level attributes such as the requested number of nodes, application models define the actual load executed on the system. ElastiSim introduces phases and tasks to define an application model. Each application model consists of phases, and each phase comprises tasks representing system activities such as computation, communication, or I/O operations. To allow the reconfiguration of malleable applications during runtime, ElastiSim introduces scheduling points where reconfigurations can safely occur. Malleable applications automatically provide scheduling points between phases to apply reconfiguration requests issued by the scheduler.

As the system load introduced by an application depends on the configuration (i.e., the number of resources) and scales linearly only in rare cases, ElastiSim supports performance models to define the load of a task executed on the system (e.g., the number of bytes to transfer). Users can define performance models (i.e., mathematical functions) dependent on the number of nodes to allow the workload to adapt to a new configuration and define its scalability. With a final attribute, the distribution pattern, users can define which assigned resources participate in the task (e.g., all ranks or root only), allowing the description of simulated clones of real-world applications.

III. SIMULATION FRAMEWORK

The HPCIO analysis repository [17] offers various real-world application traces and information regarding their execution environment. It includes, among others, the name of the platform where the application was run, the number of assigned nodes, the number of ranks, and the execution time. Furthermore, the HPCIO repository provides the application’s Darshan summary and detailed information about its behavior, such as average throughput.

First, we provide an overview of the system design. The simulation framework, as illustrated in Fi-

gure 2, consists of multiple phases. At the start, a web-based procedure collects the information that will subsequently be used by the framework in the next phases. The available trace of each application (native I/O trace) consists mainly of data volumes read or written over a specific number of time intervals. Each interval represents a sample of the application execution (all intervals have the same duration) where performance and I/O metrics are collected. The execution environments of the selected applications (native platforms) were examined in terms of I/O bandwidth and computation power.

The application profile algorithm analyzes the native application trace and estimates the duration of computation and I/O time within each interval. This work assumes that the CPU and I/O times are much bigger than the communication times. The result of this algorithm is the native application profile. It’s important to note that the original and simulated platforms are different. Therefore, we need to translate the original application behavior to the simulator. We use a native-to-simulated application profile converter, which calculates the corresponding interval times over the simulated environment.

The application profile sampling algorithm (see the overview, Figure 2) executes over the output from the native-to-simulated application profile converter to ensure accurate data distribution over the intervals. It generates the application I/O trace to be executed over the simulated platform. The simulated I/O trace, until this phase, contains two tasks: the I/O task with sampled data amount and the computation task with a certain duration. Through the application calibration that receives I/O traces sampled as input, the simulated application is configured to reproduce these I/O traces during the simulation.

Since one of the goals of this work is to reproduce the I/O behavior of the original applications within a simulation environment in which the applications are now malleable, a performance model is used. This model is tuned with scalability data and produces a malleable version of the application that can be simulated under any number of processes. The next sections provide more details about the procedures and models for each phase.

A. Trace generation

The used traces have been collected from the HPC IO Analysis platform, a collaborative initiative to enhance knowledge and collaboration regarding the I/O aspects of high-performance computing (HPC) applications. The database includes data on application performance across different parallel I/O libraries and layers of the I/O stack. The HPCIO Analysis repository provides traces of scientific applications such as Quantum ESPRESSO, Nek5000, WaComm++, and others. We have focused on two aspects of our approach. The first is the records that provide I/O data volumes in specific time slots. The second aspect is the darshan summary [18], which maintains statistics such as counters, timers, average

Fig. 2: Architecture overview.

I/O bandwidth, execution time, and other relevant information related to the I/O workload generated by the application. Figure 3 depicts the use case modeling of the QUANTUM ESPRESSO (QE) application. The figure displays the native QE trace in Figure 3a. The x-axis represents execution time in seconds, while the y-axis represents I/O data amounts in gigabytes.

B. Native and simulated application profiles

The HPCIO analysis platform provides a Darshan summary that keeps a detailed record of the application and the generated trace. This trace includes counters of I/O operations for different APIs such as POSIX, MPI, and HDF5. Timestamps indicate when the first and last read/write operations occur and when a file is opened or closed. Incremental timers denote the time spent performing I/O, and histograms of I/O access sizes visually represent the I/O access patterns. However, the information related to I/O application performance, such as average throughput, is used in native and simulated application profiles. The application profile computes the interval length T_i of the collected trace and the duration of the CPU and I/O phases of each interval of the native trace. The I/O phase duration of the interval i , T_i^{IO} is computed by dividing the interval I/O data over native I/O bandwidth (provided by the HPCIO repository). The CPU phase duration T_i^{CPU} will be the remainder time of the interval. Figure 3b shows the profiling of native trace with QE application.

When we port the trace from the native platform into the simulated one, the execution times of the CPU and I/O interval may differ because of changes in the CPU and I/O performances between both platforms. The application profile uses the ratios of the CPU processing power and I/O bandwidths between the native and simulated platforms (R_{cpu} and R_{io} , respectively) to estimate the execution time of each CPU and I/O interval on the simulated platform. This produces a profile for the simulated appli-

cation. For example, as illustrated in Figure 3c, when we run an application on a faster platform ($R_{cpu} = 0.8$ and $R_{io} = 0.5$), the CPU and I/O times are reduced. In such a case.

C. Application profile sampling

The next step is to generate an application I/O trace based on the application profile of the simulated platform. Application profile sampling processes application profile data at specified time intervals (denoted as sampling window). One sampling window could include one or more intervals. Application profile sampling takes three inputs: the amount of data to be sampled, the start time of the sampling window, and the end time of the sampling window. The output of this phase is the sampled data.

The Sampling procedure iterates through each interval entry. For example, as illustrated in Figure 4, If an interval falls entirely within the current sample window (intervals **A** and **B** in the figure), its data is added to the sample data. If the interval spans multiple sample windows (interval **C** in the figure), the Sampling procedure distributes data proportionally between the overlapped sample windows. In this case, it calculates the fractions of the interval that fall within each window (s_1 and s_2), computes the corresponding data amounts (v_1 and v_2), and updates the sample data accordingly for both the current and next sample windows. As shown in Figure 4, the sample windows 1, 2 and 3 will have an I/O data volumes of 107, 126 and 55 GB, respectively. Note that we assume an even distribution of I/O data within each interval.

D. Application model calibration

The application model calibration algorithm adjusts the computation phase of the simulated application to produce the same I/O trace as the one that received as input. Note that this trace represents a sequence of intervals that alternate CPU and I/O operations. Initially, the algorithm sets up a simulated application that consists of as many phases as

Fig. 3: Use Case (2): QuantumEspresso (PHENON).

Fig. 4: Example where the interval simulated interval time is larger than the original one. In this example, the application trace sample window is 52 seconds, and the original interval is 20 seconds.

I/O trace intervals. The I/O operation of a certain phase accesses the same amount of data as the one of the related interval. Regarding the CPU operation in each phase, the application model starts with an initial amount of computation, expressed as a number of flops. Then, the duration of each CPU phase is iteratively adjusted to meet the same duration as the one in the I/O trace. If the observed task duration exceeds the one in the related interval, then the flops for that phase are reduced. Otherwise, the flops are increased when the duration is smaller than the one in the interval. These changes are only applied in each application phase if the observed deviation is above a certain threshold. This procedure runs iteratively, refining the application model. For each run, the cumulative deviation of each execution is computed. The error estimates how the overall internal length differs from the interval length in the sampled application. The process is considered complete when the error is under a given threshold. The result of this phase is an application model that can be simulated in ElastiSim. In the QE use case, this phase is represented by Figure 3d where the application maintains its behavior, the same as its native trace but with a shorter execution time as a response to a faster system configuration.

E. Malleable application model

We define P_{cpu} and P_{io} parameters to reproduce the behavior of applications with different scalability degrees regarding the CPU and I/O phases, respectively. These parameters are part of the application model used by the simulator in the way that values of P_{cpu} and P_{io} equal to zero represent an application with linear speedup. Values of these two parameters greater than zero reduce the degree of application scalability. Figure 5 shows the effect of these two parameters on the application QuantumESPRESSO (CP). It is important to highlight that we assume the communication times are part of the CPU time.

By means of this model, starting with an application defined for a certain number of processes, it is possible to generate a malleable model that reproduces the application execution time for any number of processes. Note that this model can be applied for static applications executed with a certain number of processes (different from the original one) and malleable applications that dynamically change the number of resources. One limitation of this approach is that we don't know the actual scalability of the original application. In future work, we plan to address this by leveraging the application's scalability models like Extra-P [19].

Figure 6 depicts another example of implementing the proposed simulation platform with WaComm++ [20]. WaComm++ native trace is collected and represented in terms of execution time and data volume as illustrated in Figure 6a. The profiling of WaComm++ native trace produces I/O time and CPU time, which is shown in Figure 6b. Figure 6c depicts the native-to-simulated application

(a) Behavior of one application with different P_{cpu} values over different numbers of cores, 48 cores compose one node.

(b) Behavior of one application with different P_{io} values over different numbers of cores, 48 cores compose one node.

Fig. 5: The performance modeling of one application.

profile converter output. Since, in this example, the target system is faster than the native system, there is a notable reduction in CPU time and I/O time. After implementing the application profile sampling algorithm, the application calibration reproduces the I/O trace sampled. Figure 6d illustrates WaComm++ that is Calibrated and simulated.

IV. EVALUATION

A. Platform

Simulating HPC systems requires modeling the different hardware components that impact on the application performance, including application characteristics as well. Table I summarizes the main features of the simulated platform. Each node in the system is equipped with two Intel Xeon Platinum 8160 24C processors, operating at a frequency of 2.1 GHz. The peak performance power of each node is 3.2 Tflops. The computing nodes are connected in crossbar topology. The PFS is modeled as a shared storage tier accessible by all compute nodes. The platform has a maximum transfer rate of 8GB/s and 5GB/s, dedicated to read and write operations, respectively. The simulated network connection is Intel Omni-Path with a maximum transfer rate of 12.5 GB/s.

B. Application use cases

QUANTUM ESPRESSO (QE) [21] is a collection of computer codes integrated for electronic-structure calculations and materials modeling. ESPRESSO stands for opEn Source Package for Re-

(a) Native trace.

(b) Profiled-native.

(c) Profiled-simulated.

(d) Calibrated simulated.

Fig. 6: Use Case (2): WaComm++. Profiled-simulated uses $R_{io} = 0.5$ and $R_{cpu} = 0.8$

search in Electronic Structure, Simulation, and Optimization. QE is an open-source software distributed under GNU GPL (General Public License). It aims to foster innovation in the electronic-structure simulations area. The design of QE aims to exploit the architecture of emergent characters of supercompu-

ting through several levels and layers of interprocessor communication. The QE design utilizes the architecture of emergent characters of supercomputing through multiple levels and layers of inter-processor communication. Both MPI and OpenMP are used for parallelization to achieve the desired performance. The QE distribution includes two main packages: PWscf (Plane-Wave Self-Consistent Field) and CP (Car-Parrinello). These packages' calculation is based on density-functional theory, which uses a plane-wave basis set and pseudopotentials. In addition, there are other packages available for more specialized calculations, such as PHonon, which calculates vibrational properties using Density-Functional Perturbation Theory (DFPT), and TD-DFPT, which calculates spectra using Time-Dependent Density-Functional Perturbation Theory, and others [22].

Nek5000 is a code solver used to simulate unsteady and incompressible fluid flow while considering thermal and passive scalar transport as a part of computational fluid dynamics and axisymmetric flows. It is an open-source CFD solver created at the Argonne National Laboratory [23], [24]. It can handle two and three-dimensional domains represented by isoparametric quad or hex elements. One of the essential features of the solver is that it can solve equations on local elements without the need for intermediate communication steps, except when transferring data to other MPI ranks at specific times. In addition, the solver uses a matrix-free formulation, which means that operator matrices do not need to be explicitly constructed. This approach reduces the number of operations and memory required for simulations. All of these characteristics make the code highly efficient and scalable.

WaComM (Water Community Model) is an open-source model designed to help simulate and predict pollutant spills, transport, and dispersion in inshore and offshore environments. It is an essential component of a scientific workflow that enables the execution of numerical simulations that provide high-resolution predictions of weather and marine conditions in the Bay of Naples. WaComM uses a cloud-based workflow engine, which runs on a dedicated computational infrastructure. WaComM is an optimized version of the Lagrangian Assessment for Marine Pollution 3D (LAMP3D) [25] model, featur-

ring enhanced algorithms such as restart and shared memory parallelization. These improvements improve performance in high-performance computing environments [20].

C. Application modelling

This stage consists of performing the following steps (see Figure 2): the generation of the native application profile, the conversion of this profile to a simulated application profile, the profile sampling, and the simulated application calibration. Finally, a malleable performance model is added to the simulated application. The conversion process involves converting intervals with data volumes and computation load into an application format compatible with ElastiSim. In this way, the simulated application consists of a sequence of phases, each one including a CPU and I/O stage. In addition, Two data distribution patterns can be used for application scalability: distributed and uniform. Distributed pattern scatters data evenly over allocated nodes and is suitable for strong scaling scenarios. Uniform pattern is used in weak scaling scenarios, where the simulated environment size (as well as the I/O data volume) increases or decreases proportionally with the number of processes.

Figure 7 illustrates the results of the simulation of the four applications. The z-axis represents the I/O data volume produced by the application for each time interval. Y-axis corresponds to the number of nodes used in each simulation. For instance, a y-axis value of 32 is related to a simulation that generates an I/O trace using 32 nodes. The x-axis corresponds to the interval's number of the I/O trace. Note that all I/O traces have the same number of intervals, despite the number of nodes that have been used. This is a way of normalizing the visualization of the I/O traces for different number of nodes. In other words, all executions represented in the y-axis produce traces that have the same length despite the fact the execution time is reduced when increasing the number of nodes. Note that in Figure 7 by means of the application performance model, a new dimension is used to represent the application simulation trace for any number of processes. In this example, we have modeled high-scalable applications with $P_{cpu} = 0$ with a uniform data distribution pattern (the application data I/O volume increases with the number of nodes).

Figure 8 analyses the effect of different P_{cpu} and P_{io} parameters on the application I/O throughput. Note that the application execution times (x-axis values) are normalized in percentiles to display all the traces with the same length. Figure 8a shows that the I/O throughput of QE-PHENON when $P_{io} = 0$ and $P_{cpu} = 0$. We can observe that the throughput increases with the number of nodes. Figure 8b shows the configuration with P_{io} and P_{cpu} equal to one. Now, the application scalability is smaller, and the I/O throughput decreases when more than 32 nodes are used. Figure 8c shows the results when $P_{io} = 1$

Tabla I: Platform Specification

Specification	Value
Topology	Crossbar
Nodes	500
Processor Type	Intel Xeon Platinum 8160 24C at 2.1 GHz
Bandwidth/Node	Read-bw: 8GB/s, Write-bw: 5GB/s, Connection-bw: 12.5GB/s
PFS-bandwidth (READ)	250GB/s
PFS-bandwidth (WRITE)	250GB/s

Tabla II: Description of application use cases.

App Name	Cluster	File System	Cores / node	Ranks	Alloc. Nodes
QE (CP)	Galileo100/ CINECA	Lustre/NFS/ Swift	48	512	64
QE(PHENON)	JUWELS booster	GPFS	48	216	54
Nek5000	Mogon II	NEC LxFS-z	20	8192	410
Wacomm++	Univ. Napoli Parthenope	NFS and XFS	32	2	2

and $P_{cpu} = 0$. We can observe that the throughput increases as the number of allocated nodes increases until the 128 nodes number is used. When the application runs on a number of nodes greater than 128¹ there is a throughput degradation related to poor I/O scalability.

The QE-PHENON application writes large amounts of data during the normalized execution period from 0% to 60%. Then, during the remaining execution time (between 60% and 100% of the normalized execution time), the amount of I/O data is much more reduced (see the QE-PHENON behavior in regards to data amounts in Figure 3). In Figure 8c, we can analyze what a mixed configuration of P_{io} and P_{cpu} produces on the application I/O scalability. If we consider the execution with 256 nodes, we observe that the application scalability is degraded for high I/O data volumes (execution span from 0% to 60%), but it is kept unaffected for the rest of the execution when the I/O data is much more reduced. This means it is possible to model a wide range of application scalability behaviors by considering the different combinations of these two parameters.

D. I/O interference modelling

This section shows the I/O system interference analysis by considering different scenarios. First, the application’s throughput was studied by running experiments with multiple jobs of type QE-PHENON, WaComm++, and Nek5000. For the sake of simplicity, each experiment has jobs of the same type and all the jobs allocate the same number of nodes. The jobs have different submit times, which permits the overlap of the computation and I/O phases between the jobs. The simulated platform has more resources (CPU cores) than the total number of processes. This means that there is no resource over-subscription. Figure 9 shows different examples of the achieved I/O throughput when different numbers of parallel jobs are executed. Figure 9a shows the I/O throughput of one application when it is executed with multiple QE-PHENON jobs. It is important to highlight that in order to compare different series, the percentage of execution times in the x-axis is normalized. In the figure, we can observe that the throughput exceeds 90GB/s when two jobs are simul-

taneously run. As the number of jobs that run concurrently increases, the application throughput decreases². This indicates that running multiple jobs of type QE-PHENON concurrently introduces I/O interference because they compete for the available I/O bandwidth, producing contention in the parallel filesystem. The second and third scenarios study the throughput of one application type WaComm++ (Figure 9b) and Nek5000 (Figure 9c) when it is simultaneously executed with other applications of the same class. Note that now the throughput remains constant with the increasing number of parallel jobs. In Figure 9b we consider up to 1000 jobs, showing performance degradation for this case. This reflects the existence of I/O interference for WaComm++ when a large number of jobs are executed. Regarding Nek5000 (Figure 9c), there is no significant reduction in the I/O throughput due to the small I/O data volume related to this application.

Finally, in Figure10 we show a scenario that studies the interference over system resources through four concurrent jobs of type QE-PHENON. We can observe that the performance of a single job is degraded when the amount of I/O traffic is important (first 60% of the execution) but this effect does not happen for the remaining execution, where the amount of I/O data is much more reduced.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we propose a framework to model and reproduce real-world application traces in the ElastiSim simulator. The framework considers the differences between the native platform related to the original I/O traces and the simulated platform. In addition, the simulated applications have been extended with a performance model that permits reproducing the application behavior when they are executed using a different number of processes. We have evaluated the proposed framework by porting the application models into the ElastiSim simulator. The evaluation scenarios consider different real-world application use cases and evaluate different metrics like the related model accuracy, I/O interference, and use of malleability. Our results show that the proposed framework provides feasibility and accuracy to accurately reproduce the native application in a simulation environment. For future work, we plan to

¹Note that this tipping point value is part of the application scalability data and can be configured in the application performance model.

²Note that the figure displays the I/O application throughput of one of the applications

(a) QE-PHENON

(b) QE-CP

(c) NEK5000

(d) WaCom++

Fig. 7: I/O data volume for the four use-cases executed with different numbers of nodes and uniform data distribution pattern.

extend the study to target the application behavior with the existence of a burst buffer in the I/O system. As well, we plan to use scalability models like Extra-P to model native I/O application scalability.

(a) $P_{io} = 0$ and $P_{cpu} = 0$.

(b) $P_{io} = 1$ and $P_{cpu} = 1$.

(c) $P_{io} = 1$ and $P_{cpu} = 0$.

Fig. 8: The QE-PHENON I/O throughput located over a different number of nodes with (a) $P_{io} = 0$ and $P_{cpu} = 0$, (b) $P_{io} = 1$ and $P_{cpu} = 1$, and (c) $P_{io} = 1$ and $P_{cpu} = 0$.

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(a) QE-PHENON I/O throughput of one job simultaneously executed with other jobs. All jobs run on 128 nodes each.

(b) WaComm++ I/O throughput of one job simultaneously executed with other jobs. All jobs run on two nodes each.

(c) NEK-5000 I/O throughput of one job simultaneously executed with other jobs. All jobs run on 410 nodes each.

Fig. 9: I/O throughput of different use cases when multiple jobs are executed.

Fig. 10: QE-PHENON I/O throughput of one job simultaneously executed with other jobs. Each job runs 64 to 512 nodes.

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